

Strategic Implementation of Public Relations Practices for Users' Satisfaction in Public University Libraries in South-East, Nigeria

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Abstract

Purpose: This research examined how public relations strategies are used to enhance user satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East Nigeria.

Methodology: The study adopted a descriptive research design, involving a population of one hundred and sixty-eight (168) academic librarians from six (6) public university libraries—three (3) federal and three (3) state—in Abia, Imo, and Enugu States. The total enumeration sampling technique was employed since the population was small. Data were collected through the researchers' self-developed structured questionnaire, which was validated and pretested for reliability using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.87. The questionnaire distribution achieved a 95% response rate, with 159 respondents completing and returning valid copies that contained the requested information. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, charts, mean scores, and standard deviations, with a criterion mean of 2.50.

Findings: The finding of the study revealed that librarians in public university libraries in South-East, Nigeria, are still preoccupied with the implementation of traditional public relations practices such as library publications, orientation programmes, lending services, library notice boards, reading promotion campaigns. It indicated that librarians in the public university libraries have fully recognised the essence of acquiring a variety of skillsets such as research skills, marketing skills, collaboration skills, digital and social media skills for enhanced implementation of public relations activities for users' satisfaction.

Conclusion: The study suggests that public university management should enhance funding for libraries to acquire modern tools for various activities and public relations. Properly implementing public relations practices can increase user satisfaction and help establish a positive reputation for libraries and librarians among users and the wider public.

Study Type: Empirical

Keywords: Strategic Implementation, Public Relations Practices, Users' Satisfaction, Public University Libraries, South-East

Introduction

Public relations is a strategic management tool utilised by every progressive, goal-oriented, and purpose-driven organisation worldwide. In university libraries, public relations practices are adopted and implemented as an essential management approach to foster a positive public image and enhance the reputation of both libraries and librarians. As crucial components of any university system that ensure quality, effective, and efficient higher

education, university libraries are expected to employ various public relations strategies to strengthen their roles in meeting users' learning, teaching, and research needs. Typically, university libraries serve as strong pillars for intellectual development, information management, and knowledge transfer (Arua & Udoh, 2019; Ibegwam et al., 2019; Udoh et al., 2020). They provide resources and services highly valued by the public, who utilise them for diverse purposes. University libraries can effectively leverage sound public relations practices to remain more accepted and relevant. This is vital to amplify their catalytic roles as agents of change within the public domain, particularly in a highly competitive environment and a world increasingly transformed into a digital village.

Public relations practices involve managerial activities aimed at increasing awareness, fostering positive feelings, and persuading members of the university community—such as lecturers, students, non-academic staff, researchers, and library users—about the resources and services offered by university libraries. According to Akai (2024), public relations are distinctive management functions that help build and sustain goodwill and mutually beneficial relationships between an organisation and its various publics. These practices include intentionally planned activities and programmes by libraries to remain relevant and project a positive image of their services (Ozioko & Usman, 2019). Udofot and Sambe (2021) describe public relations efforts in university libraries as strategies to reinvigorate and maintain user interest, including activities like launching awareness campaigns about resources, services, and programmes that users may not be familiar with. Libraries engage in public relations through guides, bulletin boards, displays, orientations, extension and mobile services, interlibrary loans, referral services, public lectures, announcements, book talks, film screenings, and advertising via websites, media, press releases, and conferences. These initiatives create a connection between libraries and users, enhancing satisfaction, acceptance, and usage. Public relations influence how users and the public perceive libraries and librarians, promoting sustainable resource use and supporting knowledge and development through user satisfaction.

User satisfaction refers to the overall level of fulfilment, gratification, or pleasure gained from using library resources and services, including the environment where they are provided. Yeboab (2018) described user satisfaction as the degree to which a user's needs, expectations, and preferences are met by library resources and services in a specific university library. It involves a significant level of comfort, happiness, or contentment resulting from utilising the library resources and services to meet particular needs or demands for information within university libraries. User satisfaction is influenced by clear intrinsic and extrinsic factors such as ongoing awareness of the library resources, services, and programmes; the usefulness and functionality of these resources; the design and aesthetic ambience of the library; support from library staff through positive attitudes; and the value of the resources and services. Satisfaction in university libraries can also be enhanced through effective strategic implementation of public relations activities, such as providing deliberate assistance to users and fostering a user-friendly environment for reading and studying. This may include the use of social media platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, X (formerly Twitter), Instagram, TikTok, and others to create and share engaging content such as text, images, videos, podcasts, and vodcasts, thereby embedding the resources, services, and programmes of the university libraries into the consciousness of users.

Meanwhile, the effective and strategic implementation of public relations practices to achieve users' satisfaction requires essential resources and skillsets in university libraries. These critical resources include adequate funding, well-trained and skilled librarians, a clear understanding of public relations issues, strong support from management, and appropriate

infrastructure along with innovative technologies (Mensa et al., 2023; Okeke et al., 2014; Udofot & Sambe, 2021). Technologies such as active library websites and dedicated social media handles are vital for expanding reach and engaging a broader audience with the resources, services, and programmes offered by 21st-century university libraries. In addition to these resources, having relevant skills among library staff is indispensable for the strategic execution of public relations practices aimed at users' satisfaction. These skills include effective digital and information literacy, communication, social media, marketing, writing, interpersonal relationships, media literacy, and other essential 21st-century competencies (Akwang & Udoh, 2024; Udoh & Okafor, 2022; Udofot & Sambe, 2021). It also involves demonstrating a positive perception towards implementing effective public relations practices to enhance user satisfaction in university libraries. Based on the above, this study examines how strategic public relations practices can be implemented for users' satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Users' satisfaction is the core motivation for improving service delivery in every university library. It is driven by librarians' desire to increase user patronage, fulfilling the key mandate and philosophy of university libraries. In the context of this study, users' satisfaction depends on how aware, familiar with, and practically engaged users are with the resources, services, programmes, and facilities of the university libraries, which can be achieved through deliberate and strategic public relations practices. However, despite the importance of these practices, they are often poorly articulated, inadequately planned, and ineffectively implemented in most university libraries in Nigeria to boost users' satisfaction. This has contributed to a negative image and perception of university libraries and librarians among users. The situation has significantly influenced users' preferences and their overall satisfaction levels. Preliminary observations by the researchers indicate that emerging tools, along with the willingness, skills, and commitment of librarians to carefully and diligently implement public relations practices for improved user satisfaction, appear to be lacking in many university libraries. Therefore, given this context, it is essential to conduct an empirical study on the strategic implementation of public relations practices to enhance users' satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East Nigeria, aiming to address existing knowledge gaps.

Research Objectives

This study investigated the strategic implementation of public relations practices to ensure user satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East, Nigeria. The specific objectives were, to:

1. Identify the strategic public relations practices implemented for users' satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East, Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the emerging tools used in implementing public relations practices for users' satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East, Nigeria.
3. Determine the skills required by librarians for the strategic implementation of public relations practices to enhance user satisfaction in public university libraries in South-Eastern Nigeria.
4. Find out the impediments to strategic implementation of public relations practices for users' satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Public relations practices and users' satisfaction are important concepts that have received considerable research attention from scholars across behavioural and social science

disciplines. In university libraries, researchers and scholars have examined these concepts from various perspectives, and this present study has carefully reviewed the existing literature to identify relevant studies. These studies are discussed under the key concepts of this research as follows:

Strategic Implementation of Public Relations Practices, Emerging Tools and Skills of Librarians Ogbonyomi (2024) investigated public relations practices in polytechnic libraries for effective service delivery in North-Central Nigeria. The study, which employed a descriptive survey research design, revealed that the public relations practices used by librarians involved attending to users' enquiries at the public information desks and providing suggestion boxes to collect users' opinions. Meanwhile, projectors and bulletin boards were the facilities employed in public relations activities in the libraries. The study recommended that library management create awareness of public relations practices for effective service delivery through forums such as workshops, orientations, and seminars to educate library users. Additionally, librarians should stay up-to-date with state-of-the-art facilities that can be utilised in public relations practices within libraries for enhanced service delivery.

Similarly, Shidi and Didel (2024) investigated the impact of public relations practices on the job performance of library staff in federal universities in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. The study, employing a descriptive survey design, revealed that public relations practices have a significant impact on the job performance of library staff in university libraries. Similarly, Umelo and Nyemez (2023) examined the role of public relations in delivering effective library services at Rivers State University. The study, which adopted a descriptive survey design, found that library staff are passionate about engaging in public relations activities. It identified insufficient funds to acquire public relations tools and the lack of involvement of the university and student social activities in public relations as the problems hindering public relations activities in the library.

Akim (2023) conducted a correlational study on public relations and the utilisation of information resources in university libraries in Imo State. The study's findings revealed a moderate, positive, and significant relationship between the current awareness services provided in public university libraries in Imo State and the utilisation of information resources. It demonstrated that the use of library exhibitions and user education has contributed to students' effective utilisation of the information resources in public university libraries in Imo State, Nigeria. The study recommended that the library exhibition method, which was not used in the two university libraries, should be adopted as a vital promotional strategy to enhance the utilisation of information resources.

Another related study was conducted by Gabriel (2021) on the influence of public relations practices on information service delivery and the librarians' image in federal university libraries in North-central Nigeria. The study's findings revealed that services such as lending, inter-library loan, exhibitions/displays, and user education were provided to users in the libraries. It indicated that public relations practices enhance the librarians' image among library users by improving their job performance, strengthening librarians-user interpersonal relationships, and raising awareness of the various information services available in the libraries. The study also identified the use of ambiguous language, frustration caused by poor working conditions, lack of adequate listening skills, insufficient funding, and a lack of passion for public relations activities as major obstacles to the effective application of public relations in information service delivery and enhancing librarians' images in federal university libraries. The study recommended that university library management should organise training programmes such as seminars for librarians on work etiquette, good communication skills, and interpersonal relations.

Moreover, Ozioko and Usman (2019) examined public relations practices for improving service delivery and librarians' image in school libraries in Abia State, South East, Nigeria. The study, using a descriptive survey design, found that the main public relations practices in the state's school libraries include reader's services, library notice boards, book talks, library displays, and exhibitions. It showed that teacher librarians need good communication skills, professional experience, ICT knowledge, and strong marketing skills to act as public relations officers. The study recommended educating users and the public about the library's relevance, organising library week to inform users, and training and retraining teacher librarians as strategies to enhance service delivery and librarians' image.

Another descriptive research investigation was carried out by Okeke et al. (2014) on the public relations skills of university librarians in the South-East geo-political zone of Nigeria. The study's findings indicated that the public relations skills of university librarians were poor, which negatively impacted the overall library management, particularly in designing and executing public relations activities and positioning the library in the minds of the public. The study recommended organising in-service training on public relations skills for librarians and including public relations courses in the LIS curriculum to enhance the leadership qualities and skills of future librarians for public relations activities.

Users' Satisfaction with the Resources, Services and Programmes of Public University Libraries

Aliero and Sa'idu (2024) conducted an assessment of users' satisfaction with the resources and services of Kebbi State public library. The study employed a survey research method and used a questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. It revealed that the majority of the library's users were students who used the textbooks to prepare for examinations. It indicated that most users rated the library's collections as inadequate and outdated. It also showed that users considered the library environment inconducive, while the library staff were rated as friendly. Furthermore, it discovered that users viewed the collections as relevant but not satisfactory regarding the overall resources and services of the library. It therefore recommended increased funding for the library and the employment of adequate and qualified staff.

Eghwubare et al. (2023) examined users' satisfaction with services, resources, and facilities at Nigeria Maritime University library in Okerenkoko, Delta State. The study, which adopted a descriptive survey design, found that the level of patronage of the Nigeria Maritime University library was low, as users only visited the library for reading in preparation for examinations and tests. It also indicated that users' satisfaction with the library's services, resources, and facilities was high. The study recommended that library administrators should improve the availability of current and relevant information resources, modern facilities, and appropriate services to meet users' needs and expectations, thereby maintaining a high level of user satisfaction. Oyeleye and Victor (2021) also investigated users' satisfaction with library resources and services in university-associated programmes of federal colleges of education in South-West Nigeria. The study, which employed a descriptive research design and a questionnaire for data collection, revealed that students primarily used library resources for personal and academic activities. It showed that the students expressed a high level of satisfaction with the library resources.

Ekeng and Esin (2021) also evaluated users' satisfaction with library facilities and staff attitude at the national library. Using a survey research design, the study found that users' satisfaction with library facilities and staff attitude was very high. Abdullahi and Owolabi (2021) investigated the impact of professional competence on users' satisfaction with college libraries in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study's findings revealed that professional competence significantly affects

users' satisfaction with these libraries ($R^2 = 0.268$, $\beta = 0.518$, $t = 9.207$, $p < 0.05$). The results showed that users were generally satisfied with library services, resources, and staff attitude in college libraries. Additionally, the study found that library staff had high communication skills and concluded that both library environment and staff attitude contribute to user satisfaction. To improve satisfaction, it was suggested that libraries should enhance their working environment and staff attitude, while supporting professionals with a positive attitude.

Furthermore, a descriptive survey was carried out on users' perceptions of library services, resources, and facilities at Federal University of Petroleum Resources Effurun (FUPRE) by Patrick and Oyovwe-Tinuoye (2020). The study's findings revealed that library users were satisfied with services such as user education/orientation, research support, and reference services, but were dissatisfied with internet services, electronic services, and inter-library loan services. It also showed that users were content with encyclopaedias and yearbooks but dissatisfied with library books, journals, magazines, and e-resources. Additionally, the study found that most users were unhappy with the library personnel due to their poor attitude towards users. The findings further indicated that, in terms of overall assessment, users were satisfied with the assistance provided by librarians and the organisation of library resources, but expressed dissatisfaction with the library's location, building facilities, book lending procedures, and opening and closing hours. From the studies reviewed above, a clear gap in the literature is evident. Specifically, there is a notable lack of research on the use of trending tools for implementing public relations practices to enhance user satisfaction in university libraries. Additionally, although many researchers have examined the concept of public relations practices in university libraries from various viewpoints and motives, there is a strong concern about the effectiveness of these activities in shaping the overall image and reputation of libraries and librarians in relation to user satisfaction. Therefore, this study aims to address this gap and contribute to the existing literature on the variables under study.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive research design. The population consisted of 168 academic librarians from six public university libraries in Abia, Imo, and Enugu States of South-East Nigeria—three federal and three state. The population included 48 librarians from Federal University of Technology, Owerri (FUTO); 26 from Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike (MOUAI); 54 from the University of Nigeria, Nsukka (UNN); as well as 12 from Abia State University, Uturu (ABSU); 11 from Imo State University (ISU); and 17 from Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUST), Agbani. A total enumeration sampling technique was used to include the entire population of academic librarians, as it was a small and manageable group. The data collection instrument was a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher, featuring closed-ended questions on a 4-point rating scale. The questionnaire, titled "Strategic Implementation of Public Relations Practices for Users' Satisfaction in Public University Libraries Questionnaire (SIPRUPULQ)," contained 62 items divided into four clusters aligned with the study's specific objectives. The instrument underwent face and content validation to ensure appropriateness and relevance, and reliability testing was conducted with 20 academic librarians from the University of Calabar (UNICAL) and Cross River State University of Science and Technology (CRUTECH). Responses from the pre-test were analysed using Cronbach's Alpha, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.87. For data collection, 168 questionnaires were physically distributed to academic librarians by the researchers, assisted by one research assistant from each university library. Of these, 159 completed questionnaires, representing a response rate of 94.64% (approximated to 95%), were returned with valid information. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, mean scores, and standard deviations, with a criterion

mean of 2.50. Overall, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 29) was used to code the raw data for easier analysis.

Results and Discussion of Findings

The results of the study were derived from the responses of the 159 respondents who completed and returned copies of the questionnaire. These results are shown in Table 1 and supported by the chart below.

Table 1: Questionnaire Distribution, Response Rate by University Libraries

S/N	Institutions	Institutional Status	No. of QD	No. of QR	Percentage (%) of QR
1	MOUAAU	Federal	26	25	15.72
2	UNN	Federal	54	52	32.70
3	FUTO	Federal	48	46	28.93
4	ABSU	State	12	11	6.92
5	ESUST	State	17	15	9.43
6	IMSU	State	11	10	6.29
	Total		168	159	100

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

The data in Table 1 above showed the distribution and retrieval rate of questionnaires across the selected public university libraries under investigation. It indicated that out of the 168 copies of the questionnaire distributed, a total of 159 were retrieved. The results further revealed that out of the 26, 54, and 48 copies distributed to the academic librarians in MOUAAU, UNN, and FUTO libraries, respectively, 25 (15.72%), 52 (32.70%), and 46 (28.93%) copies were completed and returned from each of the three federal university libraries. Meanwhile, from the 12, 15, and 11 copies distributed to the state university libraries—namely ABSU, ESUST, and IMSU—11 (6.92%), 15 (9.43%), and 10 (6.43%) were completed and returned. This result was further illustrated with a graphical representation, as shown:

Figure 1: Simple chart showing the questionnaire distribution and retrieval rate in the public university libraries investigation. Note: This further simplifies the data in Table 1 above.

Research Objective 1: To identify the strategic public relations practices employed to enhance users' satisfaction in public university libraries across South-East Nigeria.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation responses on the strategic public relations practices implemented for users' satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East, Nigeria (n = 159)

S/No.	Item Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
	The strategic public relations practices implemented for users' satisfaction in our library include:							
1.	Library display/exhibitions	62	70	23	4	3.19	0.78	Agreed
2.	Library notice boards	68	69	16	6	3.25	0.79	Agreed
3.	Refreshment/relaxation corners	10	16	109	24	2.08	0.71	Disagreed
4.	Library publications	71	78	10	0	3.38	0.60	Agreed
5.	Lending services	68	68	20	3	3.26	0.75	Agreed
6.	Orientation programmes	75	68	14	2	3.36	0.70	Agreed
7.	Inter-library loan services	39	74	39	7	2.91	0.81	Agreed
8.	Referral services	57	52	42	8	2.99	0.91	Agreed
9.	Selective dissemination of information services	59	76	20	4	3.19	0.75	Agreed
10.	Consultancy services	46	61	48	4	2.94	0.83	Agreed
11.	Film shows	8	36	97	18	2.21	0.71	Disagreed
12.	Book fairs/talks	53	81	22	3	3.16	0.73	Agreed
13.	Library website to advertise library activities and programmes	56	65	26	12	3.04	0.91	Agreed
14.	Social media handles such as Facebooks, WhatsApp, YouTube, Podcast, Vodcast, etc. to promote library activities and programmes	19	33	89	18	2.33	0.83	Disagreed
15.	Radio interviews	12	32	88	27	2.18	0.80	Disagreed
16.	Television interviews	11	29	92	27	2.15	0.78	Disagreed
17.	Advertising library programmes on newspapers	14	29	72	44	2.08	0.90	Disagreed
18.	Press releases	10	24	92	33	2.07	0.78	Disagreed
19.	Press conferences	9	21	93	36	2.02	0.77	Disagreed
20.	Public service announcements	16	32	83	28	2.23	0.86	Disagreed
21.	Reading promotion campaigns	62	77	16	4	3.24	0.73	Agreed
22.	Advertorials in newspapers	15	34	86	24	2.25	0.83	Disagreed
	Grand Mean					2.71	0.78	Agreed
	Criterion Mean					2.50		

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

The data in Table 2 show the mean and standard deviation responses to the strategic public relations practices implemented for user satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East Nigeria, with a higher grand mean of 2.71 compared to the 2.50 criterion mean. It specifically indicated that out of the 22 items examined, only 12 basic public relations practices—such as library publications (3.38, 0.60), orientation programmes (3.36, 0.70), lending services (3.26, 0.75), library notice boards (3.25, 0.79), and reading promotion campaigns (3.24, 0.73)—were implemented in the public university libraries. Conversely, the findings showed that key strategic and evolving public relations practices, such as social media platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, Podcast, Vodcast, etc., for promoting library activities and programmes (2.33, 0.83); advertorials in newspapers (2.25, 0.83); public service announcements (2.23, 0.86); film shows (2.21, 0.71); and radio interviews (2.18, 0.80)—were not implemented in the libraries. This represents a significant gap, even amid numerous opportunities offered by

innovative technologies to enhance public relations activities and improve users' satisfaction in university libraries. This situation can be largely attributed to a lack of skilled librarians and insufficient funding for public university libraries, which hinders a paradigm shift in implementing public relations practices. This finding aligns with Akim (2023) and Ozioko and Usman (2019), which reveal that the predominant public relations practices in libraries include readers' services, utilisation of library notice boards, book talks, as well as library displays and exhibitions.

Research Objective 2: To determine the emerging tools used in implementing strategic public relations practices to enhance users' satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East, Nigeria.

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation responses on the emerging tools use in implementing strategic public relations practices for users' satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East, Nigeria (n = 159)

S/No.	Item Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
	The emerging tools use in implementing strategic public relations practices for users' satisfaction in my library include:							
1.	Electronic/digital library section	60	67	26	6	3.14	0.82	Agreed
2.	Radio	0	16	134	9	2.04	0.40	Disagreed
3.	Television	3	34	95	27	2.08	0.78	Disagreed
4.	Cable TV	8	25	103	23	2.11	0.70	Disagreed
5.	Electronic billboards	13	25	87	34	2.11	0.83	Disagreed
6.	Library websites	61	52	46	0	3.09	0.82	Agreed
7.	Library blogs	1	34	97	27	2.06	0.64	Disagreed
8.	Library Facebook Page	1	8	131	19	1.94	0.44	Disagreed
9.	Library WhatsApp group	54	69	30	6	3.08	0.82	Agreed
10.	Library YouTube Page	0	13	125	21	1.95	0.46	Disagreed
11.	Library X handle (formerly Twitter)	0	16	126	17	1.99	0.46	Disagreed
12.	Library Instagram Page	3	15	94	47	1.84	0.66	Disagreed
13.	Library TikTok	1	37	111	10	2.18	0.54	Disagreed
14.	Library Telegram Page	1	7	104	47	1.76	0.56	Disagreed
	Cumulative mean					2.24	0.64	Disagreed
	Criterion mean					2.50		

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 presents the mean and standard deviation responses regarding the use of emerging tools in implementing strategic public relations practices to enhance user satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East, Nigeria. The data indicate that only three items - electronic/digital library sections, library websites, and library WhatsApp groups - were deemed useful by respondents, with means ranging from 3.14 to 3.08 and standard deviations of 0.82. Other emerging tools, such as various social media handles, library blogs, and electronic billboards, scored below the 2.50 benchmark. Overall, the results indicate a low grand mean of 2.24, suggesting limited use of emerging tools for implementing public relations practices in public university libraries. This finding aligns with Ogbonyomi's (2024) study on public relations practices in polytechnic libraries in North-Central, Nigeria, which identified projectors and bulletin boards as the primary facilities employed in public relations practices. However, it contradicts Eghwubare et al.'s (2023) research on users' satisfaction with services,

resources, and facilities in Nigeria Maritime University library, Okerenkoko, Delta State, which reported high user satisfaction with library facilities.

Research Objective 3: To determine the skills required by librarians for the strategic implementation of public relations practices for users' satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East, Nigeria.

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation responses on the skills required by librarians for strategic implementation of public relations practices for users' satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East, Nigeria (n = 159).

S/No.	Item Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
	The skills possessed by librarians for strategic implementation of public relations practices for users' satisfaction include:							
1.	Managerial skills	45	87	20	7	3.07	0.76	Agreed
2.	Marketing skills	67	81	8	3	3.33	0.66	Agreed
3.	Good reporting skills	41	90	28	0	3.08	0.66	Agreed
4.	Effective writing skills	52	63	36	8	3.00	0.87	Agreed
5.	Communication skills	47	90	19	3	3.14	0.69	Agreed
6.	Interpersonal relationship skills	50	96	11	2	3.22	0.62	Agreed
7.	Negotiation skills	47	81	31	0	3.10	0.70	Agreed
8.	ICT skills	30	89	34	6	2.90	0.74	Agreed
9.	Digital skills for digital contents creation	46	76	25	12	2.98	0.87	Agreed
10.	Social media skills	32	77	39	11	2.82	0.83	Agreed
11.	Knowledge of professional ethics	57	73	23	6	3.14	0.80	Agreed
12.	Collaboration skills	68	70	17	4	3.27	0.75	Agreed
13.	Presentation skills	43	74	40	2	2.99	0.76	Agreed
14.	Research skills	82	70	7	0	3.47	0.58	Agreed
	Grand Mean					3.11	0.74	Agreed
	Criterion Mean					2.50		

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

Data in Table 4 showed the mean and standard deviation of responses on the skills required by librarians for the strategic implementation of public relations practices aimed at user satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East Nigeria. The findings revealed an overall positive response to the items investigated, with a higher grand mean of 3.11 compared to the criterion mean of 2.50. This suggests that librarians require diverse skill sets to effectively and strategically implement public relations practices, thereby enhancing user satisfaction. Specifically, the findings showed that the most highly required skills by librarians for the strategic implementation of public relations, as indicated by their mean scores, include: research skills (3.47, 0.58); followed by marketing skills (3.33, 0.66); collaboration skills (3.27, 0.75); interpersonal relationship skills (3.22, 0.62); communication skills (3.14, 0.69); and knowledge of professional ethics (3.14, 0.80). From these findings, it is clear that librarians recognise the importance of acquiring a range of skills, including digital and social media skills, to improve the implementation of public relations activities and meet the evolving needs and preferences of library users. This aligns with earlier studies by Abdullahi and Owolabi (2021); Okeke et al. (2014); and Ozioko and Usman (2019), which emphasised that librarians' skills and competencies—such as strong communication abilities, professional experience, ICT knowledge, and marketing proficiency—are critical and indispensable for the effective execution of public relations practices and the delivery of satisfactory services in libraries.

Research Objective 4: To find out the impediments to strategic implementation of public relations practices for users' satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East, Nigeria.

Table 5: Mean and standard deviation responses on the impediments to strategic implementation of public relations practices for users' satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East, Nigeria (n = 159).

S/No.	Item Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
	The impediments to strategic implementation of public relations practices for users' satisfaction in our library include:							
1.	Inadequate training of librarians in strategic public relations practices	75	66	16	2	3.35	0.71	Agreed
2.	Inadequate funds for the implementation of strategic public relations activities	88	71	0	0	3.55	0.50	Agreed
3.	Lack of innovative technologies such as dedicated Laptops, iPhone, Tablets, and iPad for social media accounts for implementation of strategic public relations practices	49	101	9	0	3.25	0.55	Agreed
4.	Lack of adequate relevant skills such as ICT skills, marketing skills, etc., for implementation of strategic public relations practices	51	72	26	10	3.03	0.86	Agreed
5.	Lack of dedicated public relations unit with qualified officers to handle public relations activities	73	69	14	3	3.33	0.72	Agreed
6.	Lack of management support to propel strategic public relations programmes	46	75	32	6	3.01	0.80	Agreed
7.	Resistance to change by librarians	9	65	74	11	2.45	0.71	Disagreed
8.	Lack of innovation among librarians for strategic public relations activities	21	53	71	14	2.51	0.83	Agreed
9.	Lack of interest by librarians in launching strategic public relations practices	18	28	86	30	2.19	0.88	Disagreed
10.	High cost of sponsoring strategic public relations programmes	56	99	4	0	3.33	0.52	Agreed
11.	Lack of motivation to embark on strategic public relations practices	54	53	44	8	2.96	0.91	Agreed
12.	Time constraints to implement strategic public relations practices	61	94	4	0	3.36	0.53	Agreed
Grand Mean						3.03	0.71	Agreed
Criterion Mean						2.50		

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2024

The data in Table 5 displayed the mean and standard deviation responses regarding the impediments to the strategic implementation of public relations practices for users' satisfaction in public university libraries in South-East Nigeria, with a higher grand mean of 3.03 compared to the criterion mean of 2.50. The results indicated that all the items investigated, except resistance to change by librarians (2.45, 0.71) and lack of interest by librarians in initiating strategic public relations practices (2.19, 0.88), were recognised as obstacles to the strategic implementation of public relations practices for user satisfaction in these libraries. Specifically,

the findings revealed that the main impediments, as reflected in the mean scores, included: insufficient funds for executing strategic public relations activities (3.55, 0.50); time constraints (3.36, 0.53); inadequate training of librarians in strategic public relations (3.35, 0.71); absence of a dedicated public relations unit with qualified officers to manage these activities (3.33, 0.72); high costs associated with sponsoring strategic public relations programmes (3.33, 0.52), among others. This outcome confirms the generally low level of strategic implementation of public relations practices observed in Table 2 above. Furthermore, this finding aligns with earlier research by Gabriel (2021) and Umelo and Nyemezue (2023), which identified factors such as insufficient funds for acquiring public relations tools, the use of ambiguous language, frustration resulting from poor working conditions, and a lack of passion for public relations activities as significant barriers to effective public relations delivery and user satisfaction in university libraries.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study considers public relations practices to be strategically implemented if they are based on emerging innovative tools to enhance their effectiveness and efficiency in achieving the objectives of public university libraries. Essentially, the strategic implementation of public relations can enhance user satisfaction and help establish a strong, positive reputation for libraries and librarians among users and the broader community. However, the study found that librarians in public university libraries in South-East Nigeria are still focused on traditional public relations activities such as library publications, orientation programmes, lending services, notice boards, and reading promotion campaigns, without utilising emerging tools like social media platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, Podcasts, Vodcasts, and others to promote library activities and programmes. The findings also revealed that librarians have recognised the importance of acquiring diverse skills—including research, marketing, collaboration, interpersonal relationships, communication, professional ethics, and digital and social media skills—to improve the implementation of public relations efforts and meet the evolving needs and preferences of library users. The study identified several major barriers to the strategic implementation of public relations practices aimed at user satisfaction, including inadequate funding, time constraints, insufficient training of librarians in strategic public relations, the absence of dedicated public relations units with qualified officers, and the high costs associated with sponsoring such programmes.

Therefore, based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

Management of public universities should improve funding for university libraries to enable them to acquire essential modern and emerging tools for various library activities and programmes, including tools for public relations activities.

University library management should create training policies and carefully oversee their implementation to ensure comprehensive training of librarians, equipping them with skills and competencies in modern public relations issues within libraries.

Management of university libraries should establish a dedicated public relations unit and assign well-trained, qualified, and skilled public relations personnel with specific job roles to handle public relations activities in the libraries.

Librarians in university libraries should cultivate a strong interest and self-motivation to initiate strategic public relations activities for the benefit of both the libraries and themselves as librarians.

Librarians should develop an innovative and imaginative mindset by leveraging various technologies such as social media platforms to create engaging content about libraries and librarians as strategic public relations practices.

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